

Abstract

This article focuses on “failure to file” cease trade orders issued by the British Columbia Securities Commission, presenting exploratory data analysis to show how often they occur and how long they last. I describe methods for analyzing the SEDAR database (2025), present basic statistical results, and provide a theoretical framework for understanding the significance of failure to file a cease trade order (FFCTO). The article uses public data to analyze questions such as how the number of FFCTOs varies over time. FFCTO are essential to the BC government's policy to incentivize companies to meet their continuous disclosure requirements. There are no government costs or penalties, but an FFCTO can affect the company's reputation in the capital markets. This article focuses on FFCTOs that companies resolved after making the necessary filings, albeit with some delay. How long is the typical delay? The duration is a significant variable because shareholders' investments constitute stranded capital when the company is subject to a cease trade order.

Keywords: Capital Markets, Law, Halt, Cease Trade Order, Stranded Capital, Government Policy, Failure Rates

JEL Codes:

A1 - General Economics

B4 - Economic Methodology

B5 - Current Heterodox Approaches

C8 - Data Collection and Data Estimation Methodology;
Computer Programs

C81 - Methodology for Collecting, Estimating, and
Organizing Microeconomic Data; Data Access (154)

D2 - Production and Organizations

D22 - Firm Behaviour Empirical Analysis (223)

D6 - Welfare Economics

D62 - Externalities

D8 - Information, Knowledge, and Uncertainty

D82 - Asymmetric and Private Information ; Mechanism
Design

E3 - Prices, Business Fluctuations, and Cycles (2889)

E32 - Business Fluctuations ; Cycles

F6 - Economic Impacts of Globalization

F64 - Environment

G3 - Corporate Finance and Governance

H1 - Structure and Scope of Government

H2 - Taxation, Subsidies, and Revenue

H23 - Externalities ; Redistributive Effects ; Environmental
Taxes and Subsidies Policies

H57 - Procurement

H8 - Miscellaneous Issues (352)

H82 - Governmental Property

K2 - Regulation and Business Law

K22 - Business and Securities Law

K23 - Regulated Industries and Administrative Law

K4 - Legal Procedure, the Legal System, and Illegal
Behaviour

L5 - Regulation and Industrial Policy

L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products and Construction

O13 - Agriculture ; Natural Resources ; Energy ;
Environment Other Primary Products

O2 - Development Planning and Policy

P11 - Planning, Coordination, and Reform

P16 - Political Economy

Q3 - Nonrenewable Resources and Conservation

Q32 - Exhaustible Resources and Economic Development

Q33 - Resource Booms

Statistical Analysis of Failure to file cease trade orders from the BCSC 2019-2025

This article focuses on “failure to file” cease trade orders issued by the British Columbia Securities Commission by presenting exploratory data analysis to show how often they happen and how long they last. I describe methods for analyzing the SEDAR database (2025), present basic statistical results, and provide a theoretical framework for understanding the significance of failure to file a cease trade order (FFCTO). The article uses public data to analyze questions such as how the number of FFCTOs varies over time. FFCTO are essential to the BC government's policy to incentivize companies to meet their continuous disclosure requirements. There are no government costs or penalties, but an FFCTO can affect the company's reputation in the capital markets. This article focuses on FFCTOs that companies resolved after making the necessary filings, albeit with some delay. How long is the typical delay? The duration is a significant variable because shareholders' investments constitute stranded capital when the company is subject to a cease trade order.

The SEDAR (2025) database analysis for this article proceeds as follows. The data sample set comprises 2,680 records from 03 Dec 2018 to 23 Oct 2025, including all inactive Cease Trade Orders (CTOs). Start by isolating the CTO where the type of trading ban is “of” securities for the issuer, which means shareholders cannot trade the company. The other kind of trading ban is a “by” ban, which means the subject of the ban cannot trade other securities. Isolate all CTO entries in the database where the supporting documents are “revocation orders” or “file cease trade orders”, then sort by name and date. Identify matching entries where the company has received an FFCTO, followed by a revocation order, to calculate the duration of each FFCTO.

This article does not consider partial revocation orders in the interim. Also, it does not break down by public or private companies; all the data used here is from “reporting issuers,” which are companies with a sufficient number of shareholders that must meet continuous disclosure requirements over time. Also, this paper excludes a relatively small number of FFCTOs whose issuance dates are before the start of the data window in December 2018.

The raw data from SEDAR (2025) includes an extensive list of all CTOs by type. The data I analyze in this article consists of a table of results that includes the issuance date for each FFCTO, the duration of each FFCTO, and identifying information about the company subject to each FFCTO. Table 1 presents data on 311 FFCTO events across six companies over 6 years. That's the average number for FFCTO: 50 per year, or 1 per week. Note that several FFCTO only had a 1-day duration. The longest one was over 1,000 days, which shows substantial positive skew in the distribution of duration statistics.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for FFCTO 2018-2025

	Number of Days for CTO
Average	67
Median	22
Minimum	1
Maximum	1420
Std. Dev.	166
Kurtosis	34
Number of CTOs	311

How does the average duration vary over time? The results show that more FFCTOs have been created in recent years, although they are shorter. It is essential to study how companies respond to the threat of FFCTO: more companies are willing to go beyond the limit that triggers the FFCTO by failing to maintain continuous disclosure requirements, but companies are better at fixing them. Also, see the maximum duration of CTO decline in recent years in Table 2 below.

Table 2 presents data on all FFCTO events by year. The reference is the year it was issued, even if the duration carries it into the subsequent year. Focus on the year of issuance because that is when the company failed to meet disclosure standards; we want to investigate whether the company's failure rates show patterns over time. Companies that make FFCTO face challenges in maintaining routine operations. Do we see that many companies experience similar issues on a clustered basis?

Table 2: Annual Statistics for FFCTO

	Number of FFCTO per year	Average Duration FFCTO	Maximum Duration
2018	5	10	31
2019	33	139	1345
2020	40	48	737
2021	31	109	1420
2022	27	47	281
2023	40	87	848
2024	67	62	418
2025	68	29	92

Chart 1: Scatterplot of Time Series of all FFCTO

Chart 1 shows that, generally, there has been more FFCTO in recent years than in the past. However, there have been fewer extreme duration values in recent years. Further supports the idea that companies take this policy seriously and work to fix it immediately when it happens. However, why are FFCTO happening more often in recent years? What happens to companies here afterwards? I suggest adding several further dimensions to the analysis by providing more detail for each company. Separate for public versus private companies? Or according to the business sector?

The focus on FFCTO here means that we are comparing apples to apples in basic terms. All companies are reporting issuers that have failed to meet continuous disclosure requirements. All companies had to stop issuing securities while the FFCTO was in effect. Differences between companies in their business fundamentals, like working capital, but all companies are similar in having a sufficient number of shareholders to require routine disclosure of financial conditions.

Statistical patterns in these tables and charts suggest companies take FFCTO very seriously and prepare to deal with them when they happen. Important for companies not to leave shareholders with completely stranded capital indefinitely. Theoretical reasons for companies to treat shareholders carefully in terms of the principal-agent model. Management as agents work to keep the principal happy. All of these companies are “reporting issuers,” so shareholders expect them to continue to meet minimum standards.

Chart 2 shows the statistical distribution of duration for all FFCTO. The smallest bin, with less than 5 days, has 68 entries. The largest bin has more than 125 days and 31 entries. The distribution shows several extreme features. For one, positive skew with a few extremely large values. The measure of kurtosis of +30 in Table 1 indicates fat tails. For another, a high concentration of values with low values. The total number of observations is around 300, so the relative frequency of the smallest bin is approximately 20%. Reflects the fact that most companies deal with their FFCTO quickly, but a few take a very long time.

Chart 2: Distribution of Duration Statistic of all FFCTO

Chart 2 provides further evidence that the theoretical costs associated with FFCTO are part of the government policy framework as follows. Companies must disclose key personnel on the Board of Directors and in management. In particular, if a person was an officer or director of a company with FFCTO, they must describe the details of all other companies where they are an officer or director. The idea is that shareholders want to know about people who leave shareholders in a difficult position. A similar policy requires the same people to also make a detailed disclosure of any bankruptcy, because this is pertinent to shareholders' risk assessment.

It is unclear how to estimate the costs of FFCTO or the disciplining power of the policy. Some costs associated with the continuous disclosure requirements to lift the FFCTO are part of routine operations for reporting issuers because they represent a specific type of overhead that companies in BC cannot avoid when meeting minimum standards. For example, auditor fees

must be paid each year in full, in cash, and the auditor cannot start next year's work if unpaid from last year due to the requirement for independence from the company; if the auditor is a creditor, then they are not “independent” and can't do the audit. These are the core costs that all companies must pay each year.

Some auditors are more expensive than others and have a better reputation among investors. Is there a relationship between auditor costs and investor confidence in the company or market valuations? Is there a trade-off in which auditor fees and corporate complexity can improve a company's reputation in capital markets, while also increasing the risk of an FFCTO? Can we analyze how the ecosystem of auditor firms changes over time in response to companies' preferences by studying the number of auditors, sizes, standards, and costs?

All the data used here is from “reporting issuers,” but this paper does not break down by public or private companies. Reporting issuers are companies with a sufficient number of shareholders that must meet continuous disclosure requirements over time. Includes public companies with additional standards from the stock exchange, like one audit per year for TSX-V or one audit per quarter for TSX. Also includes private companies that may have additional disclosure requirements in other jurisdictions, such as the USA. This is a complex business context in which the BCSC has limited policy options: even when a company gets a FFCTO, it can continue operations, so what is the role of a cease trade order? How does it compare to other jurisdictions around the world?

References

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